

Bridging the Feasibility Gap in Energy Transitions:

Policy Insights from Multi- Country Stakeholder Consultations

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Key messages

- Despite growing policy ambition, **energy transition scenarios** continue to overlook social, political, and institutional implementation challenges.
- **Stakeholders across Europe, Africa, and Asia identify eight common categories of transition barriers**, including social resistance, economic constraints, policy incoherence, vested interests, administrative barriers, infrastructure limitations, skills gaps and supply chain bottlenecks.
- **These barriers are interdependent and systemic**; they must be addressed collectively to avoid technically sound but practically unachievable transition pathways.
- **Future scenario modeling and policy strategies** should integrate stakeholder-informed insights to align ambition with on-the-ground feasibility.

A **rapid, inclusive, and deep transformation** of energy systems **is essential** not only to meet climate targets, but to safeguard planetary health and **to foster sustainable human development**.

Background & Context

The urgency of accelerating the energy transition has never been greater.

According to the IPCC's Sixth Assessment Synthesis Report (2023), current global emissions reduction efforts remain insufficient to limit warming to 1.5°C, and delayed action significantly raises the risks of irreversible impacts on ecosystems, livelihoods, and human well-being. A rapid, inclusive, and deep transformation of energy systems is therefore essential – not only to meet climate targets, but to safeguard planetary health and sustainable human development.

Scenarios are a fundamental tool in planning sustainability and energy transitions. They help policymakers explore future possibilities and define roadmaps for reducing emissions and achieving long-term goals. However, most current energy transition

scenarios are developed through integrated assessment models that focus primarily on technical, economic, and environmental variables. While these models are important, they often fail to reflect the real-world challenges that determine whether policies can actually be implemented.

One key shortcoming is the systematic exclusion of social, political, and institutional dimensions. As highlighted by recent literature and reinforced by our findings, ignoring these dimensions leads to transition pathways that may appear feasible on paper but are unlikely to succeed in practice. Political resistance, social backlash, governance limitations, and public trust are not peripheral issues – they are core determinants of transition success.

To bridge this “feasibility gap,” the SPES project undertook a series of structured stakeholder consultations between 2024 and 2025 across seven countries – France, Hungary, Italy, Kenya, Nigeria, Pakistan – and at the EU level. The aim was to better understand which barriers policymakers

and practitioners consider most critical to implementation, and how these barriers play out across highly diverse socio-economic and institutional contexts.

More than 100 high-level stakeholders participated in these engagements, including government officials, civil society organizations, researchers, energy companies, labor unions, and international development partners. The consultations took different formats depending on local context – from high-level dialogues and expert interviews to full-day national workshops – reflecting the need for both local specificity and cross-country comparison. Despite significant differences in political structures, energy systems, and development priorities, the views expressed across regions revealed a striking convergence.

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SPES Evidence

The stakeholder consultations across Europe, Africa, and Asia revealed eight recurring categories of barriers to energy transition implementation. Although the manifestations of these challenges varied across countries, their systemic nature was evident, as was the need to address them holistically. Notably, the interconnectedness of these challenges means that tackling one barrier often requires interventions in several others.

1. Economic and financial constraints

Stakeholders emphasized both household-level affordability issues and large-scale investment gaps. In France, the cost of installing a heat pump remains out of reach for many households. Similar issues were mentioned in the EU context, where high upfront costs for electric vehicles and renovations de facto prohibit households from accessing them. In Hungary, renovation costs exceed home values for retirees. In Italy, high energy costs – driven by the country's heavy reliance on gas – place a significant burden on both households and businesses; stakeholders noted that consumers are insufficiently protected by incentive schemes, limiting their ability to cope with rising prices or invest in clean alternatives. In

Nigeria and Pakistan, as well as at the EU-level, stakeholders argued that the lack of fiscal space severely limits implementation capacity.

2. Social acceptance and public resistance

Policies that involve behavioural changes or impose financial burdens often face public opposition. For instance, participants in Hungary noted political resistance to policies encouraging reduced meat consumption. In Italy, participants noted widespread public skepticism toward the social impacts of environmental policies, often fuelled by political narratives – particularly from far-right parties – that frame the green transition as being in conflict with economic security and social well-being. In Nigeria and Kenya, participants warned of intense backlash to carbon taxes and subsidy reforms due to affordability concerns. French and EU stakeholders highlighted the political consequences of poorly designed carbon pricing, such as the Yellow Vest protests.

The interconnectedness of the identified challenges means that **tackling one barrier often requires interventions in several others.**

3. Political power and vested interests

Stakeholders identified strong resistance from incumbent industries and their political allies, leading, for instance, to the rollback or delaying implementation of key sustainability and energy transition policies at the EU level. Fossil fuel and agricultural lobbies were frequently cited as powerful forces obstructing reform and slowing-down the transition towards renewable energies, particularly in France, Italy and Hungary. In Kenya, participants highlighted “cartel-like” behavior in energy procurement contracts.

4. Governance and policy coherence

Inconsistent and sometimes contradictory policies were seen as a major barrier. For example, Hungary’s industrial development plans conflict with decarbonization goals. In Italy, stakeholders pointed to the absence of a comprehensive legislative framework to deliver on climate targets and accelerate the adoption of renewable energy, and that the Italian National Energy and Climate Plan does not provide a clear roadmap for phasing out fossil fuels, undermining policy coherence and investor confidence. In Nigeria and Kenya, governance fragmentation and weak

coordination across institutions undermine implementation efforts. EU stakeholders noted that even well-designed policies often falter due to poor follow-through and lack of accountability.

5. Regulatory and administrative barriers

Slow permitting processes, overlapping mandates, and excessive bureaucracy delay project rollout. Hungarian stakeholders described renewable energy projects taking up to seven years to reach grid connection. In France and Nigeria, funding opportunities are underutilized due to complex administrative procedures. In Italy, bureaucratic procedures must be simplified to facilitate the access to funding, incentives and clean technologies.

6. Workforce and skills gaps

Implementation capacity is constrained by a shortage of skilled labor. In France and Hungary, the construction sector lacks trained workers for building retrofits. In Kenya and Pakistan, stakeholders noted limited technical capacity to manage new technologies like EVs and smart grids. Those in Italy noted that active

labour market policies often overlook critical challenges related to upskilling, reskilling, and worker relocation. They also emphasized the importance of designing both active and passive measures to protect workers at risk of exclusion during the transition.

7. Technology and infrastructure limitations

Aging infrastructure, weak grids, and immature technologies were commonly reported. Stakeholders in Pakistan and Kenya highlighted transmission losses and insufficient EV charging networks. In the EU, stakeholders noted that current electricity grids were designed for centralized production, not decentralized renewables. In Italy, it was pointed out that the National Energy and Climate Plan places considerable emphasis on technologies such as nuclear power and green hydrogen, which remain too premature to play a meaningful role in the near-term transition. In Hungary, participants identified certain technologies – such as carbon capture, utilisation, and storage – as barriers rather than enablers, underscoring the need to better align innovation priorities with practical implementation capacity.

8. Industrial and supply chain bottlenecks

Heavy reliance on imported technologies, lack of domestic production capacity, and supply vulnerabilities were flagged in all regions. For instance, France's wind industry has largely shifted to foreign ownership, and Pakistan remains highly dependent on imported solar technologies. In Italy, the energy sector remains heavily dependent on imported raw materials and gas, with national supply policies still largely aligned with a Business-as-Usual scenario, limiting progress toward greater energy sovereignty and resilience.

These challenges are not just obstacles to be managed—they are systemic barriers that, if unaddressed, risk undermining the credibility and viability of transition strategies, thus hampering the urgent achievement of climate targets. Moreover, their interconnections mean that partial fixes will likely fall short. Effective responses must be multi-dimensional, combining institutional reform, political strategy, economic investment, as well as public engagement and support.

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Policy recommendations

Given the strong convergence around the nature of implementation barriers across countries, this section presents **overarching policy recommendations applicable for all case study regions/countries, followed by two tailored subsets of recommendations**: one for the EU and its Member States, and another for Southern countries. Each set **draws from region-specific stakeholder insights to provide context-sensitive, actionable guidance**.

01.

Mainstream **sociopolitical feasibility** in scenario modeling.

Transition scenarios must incorporate governance capacity, institutional barriers, and political economy constraints. This includes modeling social acceptance thresholds and mapping stakeholder influence.

02.

Adopt **inclusive, multi-stakeholder transition planning**.

Early and sustained engagement with supranational, national, regional and local stakeholders improves legitimacy, alignment, responsiveness and impact of policy and funding measures. Structured, regular and meaningful participatory processes, including social and civil dialogue at all levels, should consistently shape policy design, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation.

03.

Invest in **governance capacity and cross-sector coordination**.

Strengthen the administrative, technical, and financial capacity of public institutions to manage fair energy transitions. Establish mechanisms to ensure horizontal and vertical coordination among governmental institutions.

04.

Design and adequately finance **socially equitable policies**, and ensure they are well communicated.

Ensure that cost and benefit distribution is fair, balanced and well-communicated. Address affordability barriers through targeted redistributive support, with a specific focus on vulnerable households, and anticipate as well as adequately respond to public concerns to avoid backlash.

05.

Enhance **labor market preparedness and quality jobs** for green transitions.

Strongly invest in education, training and skills development, reskilling and upskilling to meet the demands of new sectors that facilitate the energy transition. Support workforce mobility and anticipate mismatches through labor market forecasting.

06.

Strengthen **supply chain resilience and domestic capacity**.

Develop industrial policies that reduce reliance on external suppliers for critical technologies. Prioritize strategic sectors for local production and innovation.

Policy recommendations for EU

To **achieve socially just and inclusive energy transitions**, strengthened reforms, investments and improved governance structures are needed, while addressing implementation barriers at all levels, **paying particular attention to the situation of groups in vulnerable situations**. Based on the stakeholder consultations held at the EU level, we propose the following recommendations:

01.

Strengthen **multi-level governance** and **stakeholder engagement**.

Achieving a fair and effective energy transition requires strong, inclusive governance at all levels. Member States should develop dedicated action plans for underperforming sectors and scale proven models – such as Finland’s energy aid, Spain’s Just Transition framework, or Estonia’s territorial transition plans. Cross-sector coherence must be ensured through alignment across policy and legislative instruments like the Clean Industrial Deal and Just Transition Directive. At the same time, local governments should be actively engaged in transition planning to enhance ownership and implementation capacity. Structured and permanent dialogue with unions, workers, and civil society is also essential to build trust, legitimacy, and long-term accountability.

02.

Strengthen the **implementation of existing EU energy transition frameworks** without delay.

There are concerns about a slowing down of implementation efforts and even rolling back of key energy transition and climate policies. For instance, Member States have been sluggish in implementing rules on energy efficiency of buildings. The EU and Member States should implement recently adopted policies and regulations without delays or reduced ambition.

03.

Fill policy gaps to ensure a **fair energy transition**.

EU and Member States should fill several policy gaps, such as further supporting energy mix diversification to avoid over-reliance on imports, building on RePowerEU, and reforming the electricity market design to ensure stable, affordable pricing and reflect energy's role as an essential service. Simple high-impact national actions, such as speed limits or corporate fleet rules mandating electric vehicles, could help curb emissions.

04.

Significantly strengthen **public and private investment to achieve fair energy transitions**.

There are significant investment gaps to be filled to achieve fair energy transitions. Frontloading of investments should be accelerated to speed up the transition and increase funding and incentives for domestic renewable deployment. Coordination between funding instruments, such as ESF+, Cohesion Funds and the Social Climate Fund, should also be improved to ensure they work synergistically and avoid policy patchworks. Focusing investments on improving the energy efficiency and quality of buildings could result in substantial health and economic advantages.

05.

Improve the **acceptability of the energy transition** through expanded **targeted support**, especially to **vulnerable households**.

A fair energy transition requires long-term structural support. The Social Climate Fund should be expanded beyond 2032, with increased co-financing rates and front-loaded EU ETS 2 revenues to provide early relief. A share of carbon revenues should be earmarked for targeted measures for low-income households, such as climate dividends, low-interest loans, and energy upgrade subsidies. Social conditionalities should be embedded in funding to prioritise the most affected groups. Renovation programs must also include safeguards to prevent displacement of vulnerable tenants, and minimum consumption thresholds at a lower rate could be used to curb energy poverty without discouraging efficiency.

06.

Ensure **strong polluters are taxed** proportionately.

Wealthier households are often stronger contributors to pollution because of their energy usage and travel frequency; however, the existing systems tend to disadvantage low-income communities that face challenges in adopting sustainable energy options. The taxation system should be redesigned to tax activities with pollution levels effectively, proportionately and fairly

Policy recommendations for Global South

To improve the real-world feasibility of energy transitions in low- and middle-income countries, **policies must address structural implementation barriers while tailoring solutions to local institutional capacity, economic constraints, and social dynamics.**

Based on the consultations held in Kenya, Nigeria, and Pakistan, we propose the following:

01.

Align national energy transition plans with **local development priorities.**

Governments should integrate clean energy and climate goals into broader development and poverty-reduction strategies, recognizing co-benefits for health, employment, and productivity. In Kenya, stakeholders emphasized aligning transition plans with Vision 2030, medium-term national development plans, and county-level integrated development plans. In Pakistan, participants stressed the importance of anchoring just transition initiatives within national economic planning to ensure long-term buy-in.

02.

Establish **multi-stakeholder platforms** for inclusive **planning and accountability.**

Governments should institutionalize consultative mechanisms that bring together civil society, subnational governments, legislature, youth, academia, and the private sector to inform policy development, implementation, reporting and monitoring. In Nigeria, participants highlighted the absence of structured forums for stakeholder engagement, leading to limited public ownership of reforms such as fuel subsidy removal. Kenya's county-level engagement structures could offer a model for more decentralized consultation and follow-up.

03.

Strengthen the capacity of **public institutions to deliver transition programs.**

Energy ministries and regulatory authorities must be equipped with the skills, data systems, and financial autonomy needed to manage transition efforts effectively. In Pakistan, weak coordination between energy and finance ministries was cited as a major bottleneck. In Kenya and Nigeria, participants flagged the need for capacity-building at both national and subnational levels to manage decentralized renewable energy deployment and climate finance access.

04.

Modernize and decentralize grid infrastructure to enable **renewable integration and cross-border energy trade.**

Governments should prioritize investment in national grid upgrades and establish regulatory frameworks to support distributed energy generation. Stakeholders in Pakistan highlighted the need to expand access through micro-grids in underserved areas and improve grid resilience to accommodate variable renewables. In both African and Asian contexts, harmonizing technical standards across countries would facilitate regional electricity trade and unlock the potential for cross-border collaboration in clean energy development.

05.

Expand targeted support for **vulnerable households**.

Ensure affordability and protect low-income groups from the short-term impacts of transition policies. This includes scaling up social protection programs and tariff reform compensation schemes. For example, several Nigerian and Pakistani participants recommended using digital cash transfer platforms (already piloted in other sectors) to mitigate the effects of subsidy reforms or rising electricity costs. Stakeholders in Kenya also called for lifeline electricity tariffs for low-consumption users.

06.

Strengthen green skills and **support local enterprise development**.

workforce development with enterprise support. This includes expanding vocational training and apprenticeships in renewable energy, clean cooking, building retrofits, and other emerging sectors. In Nigeria, stakeholders emphasized the importance of including informal sector workers – such as mechanics, masons, and welders – in upskilling initiatives. In both Kenya and Nigeria, support for green Technical and Vocational Education and Training programs was seen as vital to unlocking youth employment potential. At the same time, governments should facilitate the participation of local entrepreneurs and SMEs in clean energy markets by easing licensing and procurement barriers, as in Kenya, and by introducing targeted credit lines and public procurement quotas, as recommended by stakeholders in Nigeria and Pakistan.

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